

Supporting information

Lamellar and pillared ZSM-5 zeolites modified with MgO and ZnO for catalytic fast-pyrolysis of eucalyptus woodchips

Javier Fermoso^a, Héctor Hernando^a, Prabhas Jana^a, Inés Moreno^{a,b}, Jan Přeč^c, Cristina Ochoa-Hernández^c, Patricia Pizarro^{a,b}, Juan M. Coronado^a, Jiří Čejka^{c*}, David P. Serrano^{a,b*}

^aThermochemical Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy Institute, 28935, Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

^bChemical and Environmental Engineering Group, ESCET, Rey Juan Carlos University, 28933, Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

^cJ. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, v.v.i., 182 23, Prague 8, Czech Republic.

Fig. S1. Low-angle XRD patterns of calcined PI-ZSM-5 and L-ZSM-5.

Fig. S2. TEM images of the parent materials after calcination: (a, b) PI-ZSM-5 and (c, d) L-ZSM-5.

Fig. S3. TEM images of (a) MgO/PI-ZSM-5, (b) MgO/L-ZSM-5, (c) ZnO/PI-ZSM-5 and (d) ZnO/L-ZSM-5.

Fig. S4. Hydroxyl vibration region of the materials under study before (top spectra) and after (down spectra) adsorption of pyridine.